

Acclimatisation of some Lyophobic Sols and Bhattacharya's Equation for Slow Coagulation

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The coagulation of silver and Prussian blue sols by different concentrations of electrolyte has been studied. The results are discussed in the light of preferential adsorption of similarly charged ions. Bhattacharya's equation for slow coagulation has been verified.

Bhattacharya's equation¹ for slow coagulation has already been verified for a number of lyophobic and lyophilic sols. In this paper are given the results of slow coagulation of silver and Prussian blue sols after acclimatising them with electrolyte, and discussed in the light of earlier theories.

Weiser² studied the difference between the amounts of electrolyte required to coagulate a hydrated Fe_2O_3 sol by adding electrolyte all at once and by addition in small quantities. He found that the quantity of the electrolyte required to coagulate the sol in the latter case was greater than in the former. He attributed this difference to 'acclimatisation' of the sol to electrolytes. These studies were later extended by Freundlich and Scholz³. Sen and Mehrotra⁴ have shown that in presence of small amount of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ a larger amount of KCl is required to coagulate the copper ferrocyanide sol than in its absence. Weiser (*loc. cit.*) suggested that the addition of a small quantity of an electrolyte peptised a sol owing to adsorption of similarly charged ions. Another view put forward to explain this behaviour is based on the antagonistic effect of the precipitating cations or anions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The silver sol was prepared by adding just sufficient ammonia to 20 ml of 5 % silver nitrate solution to dissolve silver hydroxide formed. The solution was made up to one litre and a 2% solution of tannic acid was added drop by drop with constant stirring, until a dark brown sol was obtained. It was dialysed against running distilled water until free from electrolytes.

1. A. K. Bhattacharya, *et. al.*, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **28**, 179, 638; 1952, **29**, 687, 759.
2. H. B. Weiser, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, **25**, 399; 1921, **25**, 665; 1924, **28**, 232; 1926, **30**, 20, 1527.
3. Freundlich and Scholz., *Koll. Chem. Beihfte*, 1922, **16**, 267.
4. Sen and Mehrotra, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1925, **142**, 345.

The Prussian blue sol was prepared by adding slowly with constant stirring a 0.2% solution of potassium ferrocyanide to a 0.1% FeCl_3 solution, until a dark blue precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was then filtered, washed with distilled water until free from $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{-4}$ ions and then just dissolved in 4% oxalic acid solution. The sol was then dialysed until free from Cl^- ions.

The purified sols were divided into five portions, each portion contained 95 ml of the sol and 5 ml of a mixture of water and uni- univalent electrolyte of different concentrations. The coagulation of each portion by uni-, bi, and tri-univalent electrolytes was studied by the photoelectric method described previously⁵. The results obtained are discussed below.

DISCUSSION

The time for the same stage of coagulation, measured in terms of optical density, first increases for acclimatising concentration of the electrolyte, and thereafter it tends to decrease. These observations indicate that the stability of silver and Prussian blue sols increases by the addition of a small quantity of the acclimatising electrolyte. These observations support the view of Ghosh and Dhar⁶ and Weiser (loc. cit.) for the adsorption of similarly charged ions on the one hand, and the adsorption of the precipitating ions by partially coagulated particles as suggested by Freundlich and Scholz (loc. cit.), on the other.

FIG. 1

In the highly purified state of the sol obtained by adequate dialysis the electrolyte content is too small, yet for the stability of sol traces of peptising electrolyte must be present. Under such conditions some of the charge-determining ions may remain adsorbed on the colloidal particles, at the same time being surrounded by the counterions. Thus,

5. A Kumar, and Bhattacharya, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 361.

6. Ghosh and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1925, **29**, 435.

a highly pure sol becomes less saturated and more capable of adsorbing similarly charged ions. A similar explanation was offered in connection with acclimatisation and ionic antagonism in the coagulation of sols by mixed electrolytes².

FIG. 2

The experiments on acclimatisation further show that the stability of the sols increases with gradual addition of the acclimatising electrolyte up to a certain concentration beyond which the stability of the sols begins to decrease. It is, however, seen from the Figs. 1 and 2 that the maximum acclimatisation concentration is the same with uni-and-bivalent precipitating ions but it is less with the tri-valent ones. This anomaly may be due to ionic antagonism.

FIG. 3

The value of the critical stability concentration 'a' of the equation, $C = a + \frac{m \cdot l/t}{n + 1/t}$

and the linear plot of $1/C - a$ vs t remain unaffected (Figs. 3--4) for the acclimatised and non-acclimatised sols.

FIG. 4

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